

A Study of Anxiety in Relation to Academic Achievement among Higher Secondary Students

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The root meaning of the word anxiety is 'to vex or trouble'; in either the absence or presence of psychological stress, anxiety can create feelings of fear, worry, uneasiness and dread. Anxiety is considered to be a normal reaction to a stressor. It may help a person to deal with a difficult situation by prompting one to cope with it. When anxiety becomes excessive, it may fall under the classification of an anxiety disorder. The intensity and reasoning behind anxiety determines whether it is considered a normal or abnormal reaction.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A STUDY OF ANXIETY IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS"

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Alaina Hellum-Alexander (2010) proved that Effective Teaching Strategies for Alleviating Math Anxiety and Increasing Self-Efficacy in Secondary Students Math anxiety and low self-efficacy create stumbling blocks in math education. Teachers must learn how to effectively alleviate these problems using the most current research and best

practices. In this paper, current research is reviewed and synthesized. It is found that math anxiety can be treated with direct interventions such as relaxation therapy, or indirectly,

ABSTRACT

Our education mainly stresses to develop cognitive aspect which deals with knowledge and to some extent develop cognitive aspect which deals with motor skills. The affective aspect which deals with emotions, feelings and sentiments of the child is totally neglected by our Education. For developing the child emotionally and socially mature, only formal education is not enough but informal education which the child gets from his family and society is also needed. In the past years, there has been extensive research on various approaches of teaching in secondary education. But no one method or approach has been found consistently superior to all. It reveals the fact that no single approach can be best suited to all the students. The most important question is to determine which students achieve more and under what conditions and also the factors which affect the achievement. An emerging area of research that holds promise in helping us to answer these questions is student's level of general mental ability in anxiety and emotional adjustment. Researchers and educationists are now attempting a thorough work in the area of general anxiety and emotional adjustment and found it a very potential one in influencing the student's academic achievement.

Keywords: Anxiety, academic achievement

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a psychological and physiological state characterized by somatic, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral components.

with teaching style and cooperative learning. It is suggested that future research focus on how math anxiety relates to achievement and the possible benefits of relational instruction in secondary students specifically.

Chinn SL. (2009) proved that Mathematics anxiety in secondary students in England. Whatever the changes that are made to the mathematics curriculum in England, there will always remains a problem with mathematics anxiety. Maths anxiety is rarely facilitative. This study examined aspects of mathematics in secondary schools and how students rated them as sources of anxiety. Over 2000 students in independent and mainstream schools in England completed a 20 item questionnaire designed to investigate maths anxiety levels. The same questionnaire was given to over 440 dyslexic males in specialist schools within the same age range. The results showed that examinations and tests create high levels of anxiety in approximately 4% of students. The results suggest that certain aspects and topics in the maths curriculum, such as long division, cause similar levels of anxiety for students in all year groups in secondary schools.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The present study attempts to find out the anxiety and academic achievement in computer science of higher

secondary students. Since the problem is concerned with "Survey" type, the investigator has selected the normative survey method for conducting the study.

The word 'survey' indicates the gathering of the data regarding current conditions. The word "normative" is used because surveys are frequently made for the purpose of ascertaining which is the normal or typical condition or practice. "**Normative Survey**" is applied in order to suggest the two closely related aspects of study. The descriptive or normative survey method of educational research is very common. It is that method of investigation which attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present in the form of conditions, practices, processes, attitudes, beliefs etc. It is concerned with the phenomena that are typical of the normal conditions. It is an organized attempt to analyze, interpret, report the present status of social institution, group or area.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Nine schools are selected through stratified random sampling technique. The sample for the present study consisted of 300 higher secondary students in Coimbatore district. The students of both sexes coming from both rural and urban areas were included in the study.

TOOL USED IN THE STUDY

The data are essential for carrying out research investigation. The data are collected with the help of the special apparatus called as tools. The success of a research must be received by selecting a proper tool for the research. So, that the investigator used the following tool i.e. academic anxiety and academic achievement in computer science.

DATA COLLECTION

In Coimbatore district, the investigator selected three government schools, three government aided schools and three self-financed schools using stratified random sampling technique. A set of management students from each school was selected in a random manner. Thus the researcher used stratified random sampling technique for collection of data from the vast area of Coimbatore district.

THE STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the interpretation of the data to draw to a more meaningful picture of results from the collected data in the present study from the following statistical measures were used.

- Mean
- Standard deviation
- 'T' test
- 'F' test

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

ANXIETY

- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their gender.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their locality of residence.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their medium of instruction.

- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their father's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their mother's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their father's annual income.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their mother's annual income.
- It is found that, there is a significant difference in the anxiety of higher secondary students in respect of their type of management.

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN COMPUTER SCIENCE

- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their gender.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their locality of residence.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their medium of instruction.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their father's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their mother's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their father's annual income.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their mother's annual income.
- It is found that, there is a significant difference in the academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students in respect of their type of management.
- It is found that, there is a no relationship between anxiety and academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students.

CONCLUSION

Overall the present study of concluded that, there is a significant relationship between anxiety and academic achievement in computer science of higher secondary students. Also it is necessary to conduct periodic teachers and students meeting in schools to improve the anxiety and academic achievement in Computer Science.

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